

The Effect of Remittances on GDP Growth in Bangladesh

Rakibul Islam

Khulna University, Khulna, Bangladesh

Email: rakibulislamcma@gmail.com

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7298743

ABSTRACT

Bangladesh is one of the highest remittance recipient countries in the world. Various studies have been done about the remittance output relationship in recent years. It is not clearly defined about the economic growth impact on remittance of developing countries. The study is an attempt to understand the impact of inward remittances flows on per capita GDP growth in Bangladesh during 1976-2015. Through the granger causality test the study find that there is a causal relationship between economic growth and remittance. The study also shows that the variation of GDP growth can be explained by remittances at a significant level. And the remittance positively affects GDP growth rate in Bangladesh.

Keywords: Remittance, GDP, economic growth, causality, Impact, VAR, Regression

How to Cite: First Author, Second Author, (Year). Type the Research Title. *LC International Journal of STEM* Volume. 2 No. (3), XX- XX. DOI:

INTRODUCTION

The earnings which sent back by the migrant workers to their own country from the country of employment is known as remittance. The earning of migration workers is one of the most important sources of money supply for the poor family in the developing countries. The more reliable and less volatile source of money supply is among the external financing sector when compared to the other forms of flows which include official development assistance and foreign direct investment (Ratha 2007).

Whatever may be the case, remittances can also have the opposite effects in the economy unlike ODA or FDI because it is an outcome of labor migration. So remittances can effects on a country economy both in positive and in negative way. There are positive or negative relationship connected with labour migration, the impact of remittances on the economy measured at the macroeconomic, household or community level in the country of origin.

Enhancing the balance of payment, fulfilling the basic needs of a family, boost local economy may be the positive impact of remittance on economic growth of a country. Remittances tend to decrease as migrant community is more established in the destination country, more dependency on remittance,

income inequalities may be the negative impact on economic growth of a country. In Bangladesh remittances began to increase in a dynamic level in the mid-1970s. The country acquired a constant established position of remittances in the late 1970s, when the regime embarked on trade liberalization by abandoning the fixed exchange rate and switching to a managed exchange rate. During the last decades the economic growth of Bangladesh has significantly improved. For instance, in 1980 Bangladesh gained 4.54 percent of average annual growth (WB, 2010) and in 1990 it became rise to 5.21.

In such cases both remittance and economic growth are increasing proportionately. So there exists a burning question whether remittance has the impact on economic growth or not? Is there any short term or long term relationship exists between remittance and economic growth?

There exists a lot of study on this topic but still there is some gap exists on the discussion of relationship between remittance and GDP or economic growth. This study tries to fill the gap and discuss the impact of remittance on GDP as an indicator of economic growth.

Whatever, this paper is discussed about the impact of remittance on economic growth in Bangladesh taken GDP as an indicator of economic growth. Starting with the introduction section the paper begins the study. Then the paper will discuss about the inflow of remittance and GDP growth of Bangladesh. The next section will discuss the related literature reviews of Remittance and economic growth. After that the next section will discuss the analysis of the study using different techniques econometric model and find out the output result of remittance and GDP relationship where data is using from 1976 to 2015 and then concluded the study by outlining the results and findings.

Objectives of the study

The objective of the study is to find out the impact of remittance on economic growth. There are many indicators of economic growth. Among them GDP is one of the most important factors. The study took GDP as an indicator of economic growth. So ultimately the main objective is simply to see if remittances positively or negatively affect growth of GDP per capita in Bangladesh over the period 1976 – 2015.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The money that migrants send back home is an important source of revenue for families, but also for developing economies. Remittances are migrant workers' earnings sent back from the country of employment to the country of origin (Judith van Doorn). Remittances have become the second largest source of external funding, after direct foreign investment (DFI) and ahead of official development assistance (ODA). (Orozco,2000). A good measure of the weight of remittances is their proportion to a

country's population, its gross national product (GNP) or other income-generating activities like merchandise exports and tourism. (Social Finance Programme ILO, 2007) Remittances can assist to reduce the budget limitation in the recipient economies and enhance consumption of both durables and nondurables (IMF 2005). In addition remittance can prompt higher growth of human capital through taking into account education and health care, and furthermore can prompt expanded physical and financial system (IMF 2005). So,

in that case, remittances have the capability to prompt growth. IMF (2005) suggests that remittance has the impact on macro economy that can enhance the longer growth rate because of large investments in physical and human capital. IMF further suggests that the impact of such outcome is strengthened in economies with well-established financial market which assist for effective intermediation of remittances in the financial system. According to Chami et al. (2008) the inflow of remittances can enhance growth through investing in different sector such as physical capital, human capital and improving the financial system in the recipient country. Remittances may help to remove the limitations as the country that keep out a large group of household from the credit market and assists to increase in domestic investment rate.

A large amount of remittance is used on education and nutrition. This leads to total factor productivity and subsequent growth. By increasing a large amount in amassing of physical and human capital, remittances can affect a positive impact on development by affecting the recipient countries' financial system. According to (World Bank 2005) remittances should have a positive impact on growth because it finances household investment in education and health, and entrepreneurship to help capital formation. Before turning to the economic impact of remittances from migration, it is important to know when migration commences, the most likely migrants come from the middle of the distribution. Migration entails costs, uncertainties and having some rudimentary skill earned through education and adequate physical capabilities. Migrants have to trade-off incentives against real constraints that they may face in going through the entire

transaction of international migration. Finally, migration flows create networks of migrants and clusters of remittance receiving regions in developing countries. The probability of a region sending migrants is higher if the region already has a number of families or households from where emigration has taken place. There is a kind of regional agglomeration economies in the migration flows. Remittance inflows into the low and middle income economies have been found to reduce poverty (Adams and Page 2005), promote economic growth (Mundaca 2009), provide capital for micro enterprises (Woodruff and

Zenteno 2007). Revenues from remittances in the country exceed various types of foreign exchange inflow, particularly official development assistance and net earnings from exports.

A macroeconomic paper by Barua, Majumder, Akhteruzzaman (2007) analyzed the important determinants of the inflow of workers remittance by using a balanced panel dataset of bilateral remittances over the period 1993 to 2005 in a macroeconomic paper. Income differential was found as one significant determinant of remittances. High inflation in home country vis-a-vis the host countries exerts negative influence on inward remittances whereas depreciation (or devaluation) of currency leads to increased flow of remittances. IMF (2005) suggests that remittance has the impact on macro economy that can enhance the longer growth rate because of large investments in physical and human capital. However, remittances also have the negative impact on long term economic growth. For instance inward remittances are by products of outflows of work force—often skilled or semi-skilled—that should be negatively affecting growth (World Bank 2005). Despite conventional belief that remittances are highly beneficial to output, the existing literature does not produce any certain result about the relationship of remittance and GDP growth. Income from remittances allows receiving families to decrease their own work and productivity, which then translates into a reduction in the labor supply for the developing country. There is negative effect on the moral hazard problem that remittances create. (Chami et al, 2003) An IMF (2005) study with 101 developing countries finds no statistical link between remittances and per capita output growth. Remittances have a positive but minimal influence on economic growth in Asia and the Pacific countries through the improvement of domestic investment and human capital. (Jongwanich, 2007) suggests that there is a direct impact of remittances on poverty reduction through enhancing income, smoothing consumption and easing capital constraints of the poor. In a work with 39 developing countries over the 1980-2004 period, Pradhan et al. (2008) find that remittances have a positive impact on growth in Bangladesh. Working over the 1976-2005 period, Ahmed and Uddin (2009) find that remittances cause GDP growth only in the short run, and this causal effect is unidirectional.

For the test of causal relationship between the time series data of GDP, and other variable, Granger causality and cointegration methods have been widely used to test for causal Relationship between remittance and GDP (output). And also for other time series variables from the late 1970's on (Kraft and Kraft, 1978; Ozturk, 2010) and there is now a very large literature. Early studies relied on Granger causality tests on unrestricted vector auto regressions (VAR) in levels of the variables, while more recent studies use cointegration methods. The key variables are likely to be non-stationary and stochastically trending and hence whether the variables cointegrate is a key issue. A study was performed by Stern (1993), using Granger causality in a multivariate setting using a VAR model of

GDP, expot, and remittance in determining the economic growth. More recently, Blanchard and Gali (2008) used VAR models of GDP, oil prices, wages, and two other price indices, to argue that the effect of oil price shocks has reduced over time.

A Keynesian simultaneous study performed by (Shan, J. and G. G. Tian, 1998) by using dynamic macro econometric model to find out the influence of remittances on major macroeconomic variables such as consumption, investment, imports and income in Turkey. The performance of the estimation indicated that influence of remittances on consumption; imports and income are all positive and reduce gradually while that on investment wears out in the second year. The impact multiplier for income implies a substantial increase in income due to remittances through the multiplier process.

If remittances have the influence in economic growth as well as have identified macroeconomic benefits, receiving economies' governments should take proper step to enlarge the inflows of remittance. Therefore the findings of this study are central to policy making. Furthermore, cooperation between governments of receiving and sending economies in necessitating easy, affordable flow of remittances is a building stone towards Bangladeshi integration.

METHODOLOGY

In the present study the goal is to determine to which extent remittance influence economic growth. For this purpose it is needed to define and explore the causal relation between remittance and GDP, a very significant indicator of economic growth.

In the very study, a search is run to find out the causal relation between two important phenomena namely remittance and Gross Domestic Product (GDP). For this purpose it is necessary for going to follow the granger causality technique. In this technique, the remittance is tagging as X and GDP as Y where X is an independent variable and Y is a dependent variable. The granger causality is analyzing of best two variables formulating the mathematical depiction of the data. The data has been collected from secondary sources like the official web site of World Bank (2010). The GDP is expressed as percentage and the remittance series expressed in current US dollar. Both series commence in 1976 and end in 2015. Using data derived from forty year observations.

Before preceding the Granger causality test it is needed to test the stationarity of the time series data. For this purpose it is required to run a unit root test. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test is widely used in this regard (Dickey, Fuller, 1979, 1981). Phillips and Perron (1988) proposed a adaptation of the Dickey-Fuller (DF) test and have developed a inclusive theory of unit roots. In case of Dickey-Fuller (DF) test, there may create a problem of auto correlation. To tackle the auto co relation problem, Dickey Fuller have created a test named Augmented Dickey Fuller test.

The exact process is either a random walk or a random walk with drift under the null hypothesis. The Dickey Fuller test involves fitting the model

$$Y_t = \alpha + \delta t + \phi y_{t-1} + \epsilon_t(1)$$

In the study the null hypotheses corresponds to $\phi=1$. Approximating the parameters of (1) by OLS has a possibility to be unable to account for residual serial correlation. The augmented Dickey–Fuller (ADF) test is useful to resolve this issue by augmenting (1) by k number of lagged differences of the dependent variable. Otherwise it transforms (1) in difference form as

$$\Delta y_t = \alpha + \delta t + \beta y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \gamma_i \Delta y_{t-i} + \epsilon_t(2).$$

It also tests whether $\beta=0$. (2) is taken in a general form and α or δ are restricted to zero for regression specifications that lead to different distributions of the test statistic.

The testing begins for a unit root in the series GDP and Remittance, which correspond to data from a random walk with a drift term of 1 and a linear deterministic time trend model, respectively. Dickey Fuller Model is used to perform an ADF test. The null hypothesis is that GDP is a random walk process with a possible drift, while the alternative hypothesis posits that GDP is stationary around a linear time trend. Again another null hypothesis is that Remittance is a random walk process with a possible drift, while the alternative hypothesis posits that Remittance is stationary around a linear time trend Hence, the option trend and intercept are used to control for a linear time trend.

Next, the VAR estimation expresses both the cointegrating equation and the short-run dynamics of the variables in first differences. At least one of the error correction terms is significant For the sustainability of the equilibrium system as they represent the coefficients for the rapidity of adjustment once the system is shocked. The generalized forecast error variance decomposition shows to what variability in one element can be explained by the innovations from the other element in the VAR system. As Enders (2010, p. 380) asserts, innovation accounting could help determine whether the model is adequate.

For determining the lag length, the most common procedure, estimation of an unrestricted VAR with the variables is made and the use of both the Akaike information criterion (AIC) and Schwartz Bayesian criterion (SBC) is made to decide on the lag length. Considering the sample size, SBC is used to chooses the most parsimonious model (Enders, 2010). The issue with the ordering of the variables is inapplicable since both impulse responses and variance decompositions are generalized. Granger causality is now required to investigate causality between two variables namely remittance(X) and GDP(Y) in the time series. As the method is a probabilistic account of causality; it uses empirical data sets to find patterns of correlation. Causality is closely related to the idea of cause-and-effect, although it can never be considered exactly the same. The point is that the variable X is causal to the variable Y if X is the cause

of or Y is the cause of X. Here the purpose is to know if one of the two variables comes before another in the time series. Granger causality is actually a “bottom up” approach. In this approach the supposition is that data-generating processes in any time series are all independent variables. In the latter phases the data sets are analyzed to determine their correlation. “Top down” approach is just the opposite which assumes that processes are not independent. Then the data sets are analyzed to observe if they are bred independently from each other. Null hypothesis for this test is constructed as lagged x-values do not explain the variation in y. In other words, it assumes that x(t) doesn’t Granger-cause y(t). Some complex procedures like f-value calculations are required for this. E-views, widely used statistical software is used to reduce the complexity. Lags are selected conveniently in this software to determine Granger Causality of the two variables. Data is transformed to exclude the possibility of autocorrelation.

Lags are chosen according to the volume of the data set. Lags are chosen as i and j to run a model order test or a model order selection method. Several values are taken and the Granger test is run several times to see if the results are the same for different lag levels. Sensitivity of the results to lags is reduced. The f-value is determined then. Two equations are used to find if $\beta_j = 0$ for all lags j: Two equations for Granger causality: Restricted (top) and unrestricted (bottom). Similarly, these equations test to see if y(t) Granger-causes x(t): Calculate the f-statistic using the following equation: Reject the null if the F statistic is greater than the f-value. In the specific case of VAR models, it is implied to test the restriction that x does not Granger-cause y. We have the regression (in y):

$$Y_t = \alpha + \sum_{l=1}^p \delta_l Y_{t-l} + \sum_{l=1}^q \gamma_l X_{t-l} + \epsilon_t$$

The corresponding null to the Granger causality test is $H_0: \gamma_l = 0, l = 1, \dots, p$. This is a Wald test, and under the asymptotic normality and consistency of the estimator, it is χ^2 distributed. If the process is not covariance-stationary, the variance of ϵ_t might change over time so the estimate will no longer be asymptotically normal and the test statistic may no longer be χ^2 distributed. In general, Granger causality tests are somewhat model-dependent (they are subject to, for instance, omitted variables bias) so should make sure to have the "right" model before running them.

To find out the impact of independent variable in dependent variable, R2 regression model is very helpful to find out such effect. As the regression model is directed, an R2 statistic is presented. The value is the multivariate equivalent of the bivariate correlation coefficient. The R2 can be interpreted as, how much variation of dependent variable can be explained by independent variable.

A general version, based on comparing the variability of the estimation errors with the variability of the original values,

another version is common in statistics texts but holds only if the modeled values are obtained by ordinary least squares regression (which must include a fitted intercept or constant term): it is in the above definitions,

Where, are the original data values and modeled values respectively. That is, SST is the total sum of squares, SSR is the regression sum of squares, and SSE is the sum of squared errors. The study is also conducting the cross sectional regression to find out the impact of remittance on GDP.

Result Discussions and Findings

4.1: Descriptive Analysis

Very first of the study, descriptive analysis is done to examine the eye scenario of the two variables that are GDP and remittance. The table is cited below

Table: Descriptive Analysis Table

	GDP_GROWTH %	MIGRANT_REMITTANCE_
Mean	4.886214	3684.853
Median	5.061206	1273.163
Maximum	7.233944	15316.9
Minimum	0.819142	18.76128
Std. Dev.	1.468724	4723.828
Skewness	-0.584604	1.365779
Kurtosis	3.078916	3.362518
Probability	0.318416	0.001787
Sum	195.4485	147394.1
Observations	40	40

From the above table it is seen that both variables of GDP and Remittance have 40 observations. The average value of GDP is 4.886214 and the average value of remittance is 3684.853. The graph also showed the minimum and maximum value of the variables and their standard deviations. For unit root test, the study constructed two null hypotheses as both of the data sets have unit root. The study transferred GDP and remittance data chart to eviews and run ADF unit root test. And got p value for GDP as 0.000 And 0.002 for remittance. Both of them are less than .05. So here the study can reject our null hypotheses for both GDP and remittance. From the rejection of null hypotheses the study can conclude that the data is stationary. Next, the VAR estimation will embody both the cointegrating

equation and the short-run dynamics of the variables in first differences. For running granger causality test the study have to first construct a VAR model for this purpose the study took the two data set namely GDP and Remittance and run VAR test.

4.2: Unit root Test

As per the methodology, first find out the unit root test for both data sets that is GDP and remittance. Here the null hypotheses H_0 : variable is not stationary or got unit root and Alternative H_1 : stationary. Before going to the technical side or estimation side of ADF model it is needed to do eye examination of the variable that might help for further process of ADF test. And the graph is shown below

Figure: Eye test for unit root test of GDP

The graph is shown the GDP annual growth rate for year 1976 to 2015.as the graph has shown that the series of GDP has a trend. In other word the series is in upward trends as time passes. So in ADF model time trend model can be included later. At the same time the study can include constant because the series doesn't involve around Zero value. Here the average sample value exists on nearer 5. For unit root testing there should have a trend as well as constant of the variables and here the data set fulfill the requirement. Now it is needed to go for Augmented Dickey Fuller test for GDP. Here we perform the test and the result is as below-

Table: Unit root test for Remittance

Null Hypothesis: D(MIGRANT_REMITTANCE_INFLO) has a unit root				
Exogenous: Constant, Linear Trend				
Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=12)				
			t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic			-4.79614	0.0022
Test critical values:	1% level		-4.21913	
	5% level		-3.53308	
	10% level		-3.19831	
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(MIGRANT_REMITTANCE_	-0.78761	0.164218	-4.79614	0
C	-225.244	158.5809	-1.42038	0.1643
Trend	26.67445	8.369644	3.187047	0.003

In our calculation we select our lag length in automatic process based on Schwarz info criteria and the maximum lag is 12. As we know that if the probability value of the variable and constant and trend is less than .05 then we can reject null hypotheses. And here from the table we can say that the variable that is the remittance has the probability 0.0022 which is less than .05. Besides the constant and the trend also have the probability which are less than .05. So our null hypotheses that is remittance inflows has a unit root test is rejected. So we can conclude that the data of the variable is stationary.

For running a granger causality test, we have to first construct a VAR (Vector Auto Regression) model for this purpose we took the two data set namely GDP and Remittance and run VAR test . With 2 lag length and unrestricted VAR chart is as below

4.3: VAR Granger causality test

Table : With 2 lag length and unrestricted VAR values

Vector Autoregression Estimates

	MIGRANT_R EMITTANCE _INFLO	GDP_GROWTH__ANNUAL__
MIGRANT_REMITTAN CE_INFLO(-1)	1.104399 [6.79319]	0.000407 [0.79904]
MIGRANT_REMITTAN CE_INFLO(-2)	-0.086601 [-0.50902]	-0.000219 [-0.41082]
GDP_GROWTH__ANN UAL__(-1)	166.9840 [2.93775]	-0.222996 [-1.25307]
GDP_GROWTH__ANN UAL__(-2)	141.1775 [2.37405]	-0.016850 [-0.09050]
C	-1177.696 [-2.90072]	5.345666 [4.20547]

In the above table there are two models and it is evident the short influence on each of the variables can be determined from their own lags. In the second case GDP growth is just replaced by Migrant

Remittance. Here () indicates standard error and [] indicates t-statistics and the co-efficient also plotted here. Here the study cannot find out the significance of independent variable on dependent variable because the probability is unknown here. So it is compulsory to know the p value. So the study needs to go system equation. The study finds out the p value of these 10 coefficient through the OLS (ordinary least square) system. And the results are

Table: probability distribution using ordinary least square (OLS)

	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C(1)	1.104399	0.162574	6.793195	0.0000
C(2)	-0.086601	0.170133	-0.509016	0.6124
C(3)	166.9840	56.84082	2.937748	0.0045
C(4)	141.1775	59.46687	2.374054	0.0205
C(5)	-1177.696	406.0005	-2.900725	0.0051
C(6)	0.000407	0.000509	0.799037	0.4271
C(7)	-0.000219	0.000533	-0.410823	0.6825
C(8)	-0.222996	0.177959	-1.253072	0.2146
C(9)	-0.016850	0.186181	-0.090503	0.9282
C(10)	5.345666	1.271122	4.205470	0.0001

from the above table it can be possible to find out the significance of independent variable on dependent variable. Here migrant remittance inflow (-1) is significant to explain the dependent variable as the probability is lower than .05. On the other hand lag 2 variable is not significant to explain the dependent variable as the probability is 0.61 which is more than .05. In the same way the study can check all the independent variable whether they are significant or not.

Now the study needs to find out whether migration remittance inflow lag 1 and lag 2 jointly influence the dependent variable or not for equation 1. For this evaluation the study needs to test the wald test and the results are shown below

Table: wald test analysis.

Test Statistic	Value	df	Probability
Chi-square	2260.013	2	0.0000

Null Hypothesis: $C(1)=C(2)=0$

Null Hypothesis Summary:

Normalized Restriction (= 0)	Value	Std. Err.
C(1)	1.104399	0.162574
C(2)	-0.086601	0.170133

Here the null hypotheses is $C(1) = 0$ and $C(2) = 0$. the probability of the test is 0.000 so here null hypotheses is rejected so C(1) and C(2) has some value so here the independent variable remittance has some influence on dependent variable GDP.

4.4: Least square analysis

Table: Least square analysis

Variable	Coefficient	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	4.303277	16.67252	0.0000
MIGRANT_REMITTANCE _INFLO	0.000158	3.643382	0.0008
R-squared	0.73426	Mean dependent var	4.886214
Adjusted R-squared	0.591605	S.D. dependent var	1.468724
S.E. of regression	1.280923	Akaike info criterion	3.381745
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000801		

From the above table it can be concluded that the value is significant because the P value is less than .05. So here the independent variable is significant to explain the dependent variable. And here the dependent variable is GDP and the independent variable is remittance. Here the regression line fitted with the data strongly because here the value of r-square is more than 60%. Higher the R-square better the data fitted for model. And the value of R-squared is 0.73426 or 73.426%. So it is concluded that 73.426% variation of dependent variable that is GDP can be explained by remittance, the independent variable. There exists positive impact of remittance on GDP or economic growth.

CONCLUSION

Day to day income from remittance has been increased more widely than before. Income from remittances in Bangladesh has also increased over its liberalization era that starts from 1979. In 2008 Bangladesh took 9th position for getting the highest remittances. Besides the growth of GDP has also been increased than before. From the above discussion it can be stated that remittance and GDP have significant impact on each other in the terms of determining each of them in a certain time scale. The goal of this research is to find out the extent to which they influence each other. From the results and discussion from Granger Causality test, it is evident that as a single factor remittance has remarkable impact on determining the volume of economic growth in a particular economy as Bangladesh. There might be other factor but it is very much noticeable that remittance alone can change the dimensions of economic growth as it significantly affects the most important indicator of economic growth GDP. In the literature review, the study finds some gaps between the relationship of remittance and GDP. Our study fills that gap by finding out the above result and discussion. The study used VAR test for granger causality and find out that remittance has an impact on GDP growth. There exists relationship between remittance and GDP. There can be exists another area of research that goes beyond the scope of this paper, such study can assume that an increase in GDP may have caused institutional development to bring more remittances through formal channels than before.

From the analysis of the paper, more study can take place. For example: the relationship between remittance and GDP for top remittance recipient economies, the long run and short run relationships of GDP and remittance. These issues are, of course, intriguing, and thus left for future research.

REFERENCES

- Adams, R., Page, J., “Do international migration and remittances reduce poverty in developing countries?”, *World Development*, 33(10), 2005, pp. 1645-1669
- Ahmed, H.A., Uddin, M.G.S., “Export, imports, remittance, and growth in Bangladesh: an empirical analysis”, *Trace and Development Review*, 2(2), 2009, pp. 79-92.
- Barjas A, Chami R, Fullenkamp C, Gapen M and Montiel P (2009) “Do Workers Remittances Promote Economic Growth?” IMF Working Paper 153/2009.
- Blanchard, O. J. and J. Galí. 2008. The macroeconomic effects of oil price shocks: why are the

- 2000s so different from the 1970s? In: International Dimensions of Monetary Policy. University of Chicago Press. J. Galí and M. J. Gertler, Eds. Chicago.
- Chami, Ralph, Adolfo Barajas, Thomas Cosimano, Connel Fullenkamp, Micheal Gapen and Peter Montiel (2008) “Macroeconomic Consequences of Remittances” Occasional Paper No. 259, International Monetary Fund
- Chami, R., Fullenkamp, C. and Jahjah, S. (2003). ‘Are migrant remittance flows a source of capital for development?’, IMF Working Paper, International Monetary Fund, Washington D.C.
- Faini, R (2006), “Development, trade, and migration”, Proceedings from the ABCDE Europe Conference, 1-2, 2002, pp. 85-116 Aggarwal et al. (2006):
- Granger, C. W. J. 1969. Investigating causal relations by econometric models and crossspectral methods. *Econometrica* 37: 424-438
- Giuliano, P. and Ruiz-Arranz, M. (2009). ‘Remittances, financial development and growth’, *Journal of Development Economics*, forthcoming.
- International Monetary Fund (2005) “Two Current Issues Facing Developing Countries” in *World Economic Outlook*
- Jongwanich, J., “Workers’ remittances, economic growth, and poverty in developing Asia and the Pacific countries”, UNESCAP working paper, WP/07/01, 2007.
- Judith van Doorn (2007), “Social Finance Programme ILO”
- Lopez H, Molina L and Bussolo M (2007) “Remittances and the Real Exchange Rate” *World Bank Policy Research Paper* 4213.
- Mohapatra N (2009) “Micro remittance from Mumbai to Apnagaon” *Inclusion: Mainstreaming the Marginalised*, S<OCH Summit, Saluting Best Practices, 2010.
- Mundaca B. G (2009) “Remittances, Financial Market Development, and Economic Growth:

- The Case of Latin America and the Caribbean,” Review of Development Economics, 13, 288-2009.
- Orozco M and Fedewa R (2005) “Leveraging Efforts on Remittances and Financial Intermediation” Report Commissioned by the Inter-American Development Bank.
- Pradhan, G., Upadhyay, M., Upadhyaya, K., (2008) “Remittances and economic growth in Developing countries”, European Journal of Development Research, 20(3), 497-506
- Rajan R and Subramanian A (2005) “What Undermines Aid’s Impact on Growth?” NBER Working Paper, 11657.
- Shan, J. and G. G. Tian, (1998), “Causality between Exports and Economic Growth: The Empirical Evidence From Shanghai,” Australian Economic Papers, 37(2), 195-202.
- Stern, D. I. 1993. remittance use and economic growth in the USA: a multivariate approach. growth Economics 15: 137-150.
- Vargas-Silva, C., Jha, S., Sugiyarto, G., (2009) Remittances in Asia: Implications for the fight against poverty and the pursuit of economic growth, Asian Development Bank (ADB) Economics Working Paper Series 182, pp. 1-37
- Woodruff C and Zenteno R (2007) “Migration Networks and Microenterprises in Mexico,” Journal of Development Economics, 82, 509-528.